

A Comparative Analysis Of Algorithmic & Formulaic Fit For Time Series Forecasting Methods

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This paper aims to demonstrate three forecasting methods namely: decomposition, exponential smoothing, and regression approaches for a given set of company data over a 50-month period. An analysis of running the following forecasting methods is discussed along with recommendations on the fit and suitability of these methods based on the given data and expected outcome.

INTRODUCTION

Forecasting involves predicting the future and making informed guesses based on historical data and knowledge of any future events that might affect the forecast (Hyndman and Athanasopoulos, 2021). Forecasting is a crucial aspect of every organisation as accurate data enables them to anticipate future needs, create effective and efficient plans, make smarter decisions, and adapt their strategies (Anderson et al., 2017; Hyndman and Athanasopoulos, 2021). Nowadays, almost every decision made by executive and business leaders consider some kind of forecast (Chambers et al., 1971). Accurate predictions are a necessity in an organisation and businesses who are able to generate sound forecasts have an advantage over those who do not practice it (Chambers et al., 1971; Hyndman and Athanasopoulos, 2021).

Depending on the data that is available, a forecast can be classified as quantitative or qualitative. Qualitative forecasts rely on expert judgment while quantitative forecasting is based on numerical information (Makridakis et al., 1998). The time horizon of a forecast can range from as long as several years like in case of capital investments or as short a few minutes as in cases of software companies who deal with critical system disruptions (Hyndman and Athanasopoulos, 2021).

Due to the increasing complexity of businesses and management problems, different methods of forecasting have been developed. Each particular method has its own unique usage and application for a particular technique (Chambers et. al., 1971). The choice of method depends on a multitude of factors like the availability of historical data, the time period to be forecasted, the degree of accuracy required, the predictability of the quantity to be forecast, the tools, technology or software to be used, and the manpower available for making the necessary data gathering and analysis (Chambers et al., 1971; Hyndman and Athanasopoulos, 2021).

For a particular set of corporate data over a 50-month period, this research intends to demonstrate three forecasting methods: decomposition, exponential smoothing, and regression approaches. The fit and applicability of the following forecasting methods based on the given data and projected outcome are examined, as well as recommendations on how to execute them.

EXPLORATORY ANALYSIS OF GIVEN DATA

The given data set contains the monthly demand for domestic, export, and OEM sales for a company. The domestic and export sales for a 50-month period while OEM data is on a quarterly basis over the same 50-month period. The data set is a time series which means that the data points are sequentially ordered in time (Hyndman and Athanasopoulos, 2021).

For this paper, the goal is to make a forecast for the next year by applying regression, exponential smoothing, and decomposition methods. Table 01 shows the raw figures.

Table 01 - Raw sales data for 50-month period

Month	Domestic	Export	OEM
1	804	1108	174
2	680	974	
3	711	1072	
4	775	944	250
5	1014	996	
6	1480	1073	
7	1407	1044	260
8	1283	927	
9	1206	1020	
10	1333	1003	370
11	1622	838	
12	1947	902	
13	1830	805	599
14	1644	884	
15	1504	1055	
16	1613	967	470
17	1821	1036	
18	1941	1077	
19	1802	906	580
20	1664	732	
21	1598	763	
22	1712	719	620
23	2028	751	
24	2573	918	
25	2349	870	630
26	1941	774	
27	1719	934	
28	1834	944	650
29	2327	1088	
30	2785	896	
31	2508	869	590
32	2128	825	
33	2101	871	
34	1968	1050	704
35	1992	1019	
36	2973	891	
37	2635	823	733
38	2306	839	
39	2358	913	
40	2121	1107	600
41	2265	748	
42	3116	700	
43	2711	883	700
44	2447	1028	
45	2489	938	
46	2181	816	813
47	2369	1098	
48	3211	1010	
49	2544	931	997
50	2447	951	

Before running the forecasting algorithms, we need to prepare the data and have an understanding of what is available and what is required. Hyndman and Athanasopoulos (2021) points out that the first thing to do when analysing data is to plot it. By visualising the data

through the use of graphs, we can see patterns, trends, changes over time and the relationship between the variables (Makridakis et al., 1998). The graph for each sales category is discussed in more detail in subsequent sections below.

Makridakis et al. (1998) also notes that in addition to graphics, a numerical summary is also important. In order to see numerical insights, the 50-month data is grouped by year; months 1-12 denote Year 1, months 13-24 denotes Year 2, months 25-36 is Year 3, months 37-48 is Year 4. The remaining two months, month 49 and 50 will be a part of Year 5 and the remaining values will be forecasted (see Table 02).

Table 02 - Raw sales data for 50-month period grouped by year

Month	Domestic	Export	OEM
1	804	1108	174
2	680	974	
3	711	1072	
4	775	944	250
5	1014	996	
6	1480	1073	
7	1407	1044	260
8	1283	927	
9	1206	1020	
10	1333	1003	370
11	1622	838	
12	1947	902	
13	1830	805	599
14	1644	884	
15	1504	1055	
16	1613	967	470
17	1821	1036	
18	1941	1077	
19	1802	906	580
20	1664	732	
21	1598	763	
22	1712	719	620
23	2028	751	
24	2573	918	
25	2349	870	630
26	1941	774	
27	1719	934	
28	1834	944	650
29	2327	1088	
30	2785	896	
31	2508	869	590
32	2128	825	
33	2101	871	
34	1968	1050	704
35	1992	1019	
36	2973	891	
37	2635	823	733
38	2306	839	
39	2358	913	
40	2121	1107	600
41	2265	748	
42	3116	700	
43	2711	883	700
44	2447	1028	
45	2489	938	
46	2181	816	813
47	2369	1098	
48	3211	1010	
49	2544	931	997
50	2447	951	

The total sales units for each year are summarised in Table 03. We can see from the table that Domestic sales account for the largest share followed by Export and OEM.

Table 03 - Total sales figures (in units) per year for each category

	Total	Domestic	Export	OEM
Total	153,887	97,817	46,330	9,740
Year 1	27,217	14,262	11,901	1,054
Year 2	34,612	21,730	10,613	2,269
Year 3	40,230	26,625	11,031	2,574
Year 4	43,958	30,209	10,903	2,846
Year 5 (1st 2 months)	7,870	4,991	1,882	997

Table 04 shows the sales figures as percentages. For the Domestic category, the market has shown an increase in Year 4. Export, on the other hand, recorded a high market percentage for Year 1. However, the subsequent years have seen a decline. For OEM, the highest figure was recorded in Year 2. Data for Year 5 is not considered in the rankings as it is still incomplete.

Table 04 - Sales percentage per year for each category

	Total	Domestic	Export	OEM
Total	100.00	63.56	30.11	6.33
Year 1	100.00	52.40	43.73	3.87
Year 2	100.00	62.78	30.66	6.56
Year 3	100.00	66.18	27.42	6.40
Year 4	100.00	68.72	24.80	6.47
Year 5 (1st 2 months)	100.00	63.42	23.91	12.67

Table 05 shows the results of basic statistical analysis performed on the given data set. It should be noted that OEM does not exhibit any duplicate values. Computing the total figures, percentages, mean, and median will help us validate later on if the results of running the forecasting methods fall within the bounds of the given data set.

Table 05 - Mean, median, mode and range for the 50-month data set

	Domestic	Export	OEM
Mean	1956	927	573
Median	1958	929	600
Mode	1941	944	#N/A

In the data analysis, Microsoft Excel and its default tools were used for all operations. For optimising certain results, the add-in program Solver was used. Forecasted figures were also rounded up and presented as integers. As such, some variations in floating point precision might be observed in the results when running the models on different platforms.

FORECASTING THE DOMESTIC DEMAND

Domestic Demand consists of 50 monthly data points. Figure 01 shows the line graph of these data points. Table 06 shows Domestic Demand grouped by year and Figure 02 shows its graph. It can be seen from the graph that a trend and seasonality appears for Domestic Demand. Trend is defined as the increase or decrease of the value and seasonality is the repeating cycle in the series (Anderson et al., 2017). A spike in numbers is observed during June and December.

Figure 01 - Line graph showing 50 months of domestic demand

Table 06 - Domestic demand grouped by year

Yearly Domestic Demand by Month			
Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
804	1830	2349	2635
680	1644	1941	2306
711	1504	1719	2358
775	1613	1834	2121
1014	1821	2327	2265
1480	1941	2785	3116
1407	1802	2508	2711
1283	1664	2128	2447
1206	1598	2101	2489
1333	1712	1968	2181
1622	2028	1992	2369
1947	2573	2973	3211

Figure 02 - Line graph showing yearly domestic demand

When Regression is run on these data points the following results are generated on Excel (see Table 07). It should be noted that the Standard Error returned is high. This affects the precision of the model. The coefficients (Intercept and Month) will be used on calculating the forecasted values.

Table 07 - Domestic demand regression output in Excel

SUMMARY OUTPUT								
<i>Regression Statistics</i>								
Multiple R	0.857484878							
R Square	0.735280317							
Adjusted R Square	0.729765323							
Standard Error	315.9462058							
Observations	50							
ANOVA								
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>			
Regression	1	13308656.98	13308656.98	133.3238797	0			
Residual	48	4791456.238	99822.00496					
Total	49	18100113.22						
	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>	<i>Lower 95.0%</i>	<i>Upper 95.0%</i>
Intercept	1044.686531	90.72057347	11.51543129	2.04794E-15	862	1227.09247	862.2805924	1227.092469
Month	35.75111645	3.096247273	11.54659602	1.86048E-15	30	41.9765388	29.52569406	41.97653883

Figure 03 shows the generated Residual Plot. It is observed that there is no obvious pattern of the spread of the residuals hence there is no issue with heteroscedasticity. There is equal variance if we move along the horizontal axis and no outliers are observed.

Figure 03 - Actual domestic demand vs predicted domestic demand

Figure 04 - Monthly Residual Plot for Domestic demand

Figure 05 - Domestic Demand residuals histogram

Figure 05 shows the histogram of the residuals generated. It shows that it follows a Normal Distribution (bell curve). The residuals are then used to do a Durbin-Watson which yields a result of 1.16. This value is less than 2 which indicates a positive autocorrelation.

Going back to Table 08, Intercept value is at 1044.69 and Month is at 35.71. This means that at time 0 before month start, the domestic figure is at 1044.69 and for every increase of time per month, it is expected that domestic regression will increase by 35.71 units.

Table 08 - Domestic demand forecasted values for the next 12 months using regression method

Forecast for the next months	
F51	2868
F52	2904
F53	2939
F54	2975
F55	3011
F56	3047
F57	3082
F58	3118
F59	3154
F60	3190
F61	3225
F62	3261

Next method to run is exponential smoothing. For time series data that exhibits trend and seasonality, Holt-Winters' method is used (Gardner, 1985; Holt, 1957; Winters, 1960). Domestic demand exhibits seasonal variation increases over time hence the multiplicative model will be used. Figure 06 shows the equations that will be used for Holt-Winters' multiplicative method. The following equations were translated into an Excel spreadsheet for computation. α β γ are smoothing constants between 0 and 1. For Domestic Demand, the values used are $\alpha=0.1$, $\beta=0.2$, $\gamma=0.3$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Level:} \quad L_t &= \alpha \frac{Y_t}{S_{t-s}} + (1 - \alpha)(L_{t-1} + b_{t-1}) \\
 \text{Trend:} \quad b_t &= \beta(L_t - L_{t-1}) + (1 - \beta)b_{t-1} \\
 \text{Seasonal:} \quad S_t &= \gamma \frac{Y_t}{L_t} + (1 - \gamma)S_{t-s} \\
 \text{Forecast:} \quad F_{t+m} &= (L_t + b_t m)S_{t-s+m}
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 06 - Holt-Winters's equations

The results of the computation are shown in Table 09 while the forecasted values for the next 12 months are in Table 10.

Table 09 - Table of computation for domestic demand using Holt-Winters method

t	Y	L	T	S	F
1	804			0.056373580	
2	680			0.047679147	
3	711			0.049852756	
4	775			0.054340205	
5	1014			0.071098023	
6	1480			0.103772262	
7	1407			0.098653765	
8	1283			0.089959332	
9	1206			0.084560370	
10	1333			0.093465152	
11	1622			0.113728790	
12	1947	14262	0	0.136516618	
13	1830	16082.0	364.0002985	0.046251711	804
14	1644	18249.4	724.6899097	0.045288473	784
15	1504	20093.6	948.5839922	0.049059401	946
16	1613	21906.3	1121.407361	0.053395462	1143
17	1821	23286.2	1173.103526	0.064881905	1637
18	1941	23883.8	1058.005877	0.085929992	2538
19	1802	24274.2	924.4875084	0.080483179	2461
20	1664	24528.6	790.4581296	0.072639338	2267
21	1598	24676.9	662.0324105	0.067240666	2141
22	1712	24636.7	521.5935341	0.071777018	2368
23	2028	24425.7	375.0648583	0.084216756	2861
24	2573	24205.4	256.0002712	0.098734478	3386
25	2349	27094.0	782.5178915	0.04104067	1131
26	1941	29374.7	1082.158946	0.042753865	1262
27	1719	30915.1	1173.804076	0.045732161	1494
28	1834	32314.8	1218.975255	0.048693395	1713
29	2327	33766.9	1265.603283	0.05666151	2176
30	2785	34770.3	1213.1553	0.070618174	3010
31	2508	35501.3	1116.72274	0.065774985	2896
32	2128	35885.7	970.2715827	0.058958882	2660
33	2101	36295.0	858.0711381	0.054160942	2478
34	1968	36179.6	663.3748017	0.055744597	2667
35	1992	35524.0	399.5806689	0.062326188	3103
36	2973	35342.3	283.3305794	0.07151916	3547
37	2635	38483.5	854.9097264	0.035392952	1462
38	2306	40798.3	1146.873564	0.038360957	1682
39	2358	42906.7	1339.192422	0.041376024	1918
40	2121	44177.2	1325.439162	0.04308622	2154
41	2265	44949.8	1214.871589	0.047771252	2578
42	3116	45960.6	1174.0712	0.057096266	3260
43	2711	46542.9	1055.702587	0.052847201	3100
44	2447	46989.1	933.8012624	0.047233038	2806
45	2489	47726.1	894.4565544	0.043535091	2596
46	2181	47671.0	704.5420242	0.043454993	2710
47	2369	47339.0	497.22484	0.046779381	3015
48	3211	47542.3	438.441975	0.052830056	3421
49	2544	50370.5	916.4016967	0.03023303	1698
50	2447	52537.1	1166.439395	0.033513328	1967

Table 10 - Domestic demand forecasted values for the next 12 months using Holt-Winters method

Forecast for the next months	
F51	2222
F52	2364
F53	2677
F54	3266
F55	3085
F56	2812
F57	2643
F58	2689
F59	2949
F60	3392
F61	1941
F62	2152

Figure 07 - Actual domestic demand vs forecasted value using Holt-Winters method

FORECASTING THE EXPORT DEMAND

Export Demand also has 50 data points and the line graph below shows these. Table 11 shows Export Demand grouped by year and Figure 09 shows its graph. Unlike Domestic Demand, Export demand does not exhibit any perceived trend and seasonality. The spike in figures also varies by year. In Year 1, January recorded the highest figure, in Year 2 it was in June, May in Year 3, and April in Year 4.

Figure 08 - Line graph showing 50 months of export demand

Table 11 - Export demand grouped by year

Yearly Export Demand by Month			
Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
1108	805	870	823
974	884	774	839
1072	1055	934	913
944	967	944	1107
996	1036	1088	748
1073	1077	896	700
1044	906	869	883
927	732	825	1028
1020	763	871	938
1003	719	1050	816
838	751	1019	1098
902	918	891	1010

Figure 09 - Line graph showing yearly export demand

When Regression is run on these data points the following results are generated on Excel (see Table 12). Unlike in Domestic Demand, the Standard Error returned for Export is lower. The value for Month is negative which means that our dependent variable will decrease by the value of the coefficient.

Table 12 - Export demand regression output in Excel

SUMMARY OUTPUT								
Regression Statistics								
Multiple R	0.197572654							
R Square	0.039034954							
Adjusted R Square	0.019014848							
Standard Error	111.3655915							
Observations	50							
ANOVA								
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>			
Regression	1	24181.84144	24181.84144	1.94978764	0.16903398			
Residual	48	595310.1586	12402.29497					
Total	49	619492						
	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>	<i>Lower 95.0%</i>	<i>Upper 95.0%</i>
Intercept	965.4604082	31.97743837	30.1919246	7.07761E-33	901.1654591	1029.755357	901.1654591	1029.755357
Month	-1.523937575	1.091373793	-1.396347965	0.16903398	-3.71829166	0.670416507	-3.718291657	0.670416507

Figure 10 shows the generated Residual Plot. Same as with Domestic Demand, there is no obvious pattern of the spread of the residuals and there is no issue with heteroscedasticity.

Figure 10 - Monthly residual plot for export demand

Figure 11 - Actual export demand vs predicted export demand

Figure 12 - Export demand residuals histogram

Figure 12 shows the residuals histogram for Export Demand. Same as with Domestic, it also follows normal distribution. Computing the Durbin-Watson value for Export gives us 1.27. This is less than 2 which also note a positive autocorrelation. By using the coefficient values, we compute the forecast for Export Demand as shown below.

Table 13 - Export demand forecasted values for the next 12 months using regression method

Forecast for the next months	
F51	888
F52	886
F53	885
F54	883
F55	882
F56	880
F57	879
F58	877
F59	876
F60	874
F61	873
F62	871

Since no trend and seasonality is observed for Export Demand, Simple Exponential Smoothing (SES) will be used. This method is suitable for forecasting data without any seasonal or trend pattern (Hyndman and Athanasopoulos, 2021). The formula shown below is used for computing using SES.

$$F_{t+1} = \alpha Y_t + (1 - \alpha) F_t.$$

Table 14 shows the computation using SES. The value for α is set to 0.2 for this computation. This will yield a forecasted result of 952 for month 51. While SES is simple to use, it is limited only for forecasting one period ahead hence the forecasted results for months 52-62 is the same.

Table 14 - Export demand computation using SES

Month	Export Demand	F	E
1	1108	1108.00	0.00
2	974	1108.00	-134.00
3	1072	1081.20	-9.20
4	944	1079.36	-135.36
5	996	1052.29	-56.29
6	1073	1041.03	31.97
7	1044	1047.42	-3.42
8	927	1046.74	-119.74
9	1020	1022.79	-2.79
10	1003	1022.23	-19.23
11	838	1018.39	-180.39
12	902	982.31	-80.31
13	805	966.25	-161.25
14	884	934.00	-50.00
15	1055	924.00	131.00
16	967	950.20	16.80
17	1036	953.56	82.44
18	1077	970.05	106.95
19	906	991.44	-85.44
20	732	974.35	-242.35
21	763	925.88	-162.88
22	719	893.30	-174.30
23	751	858.44	-107.44
24	918	836.95	81.05
25	870	853.16	16.84
26	774	856.53	-82.53
27	934	840.02	93.98
28	944	858.82	85.18
29	1088	875.86	212.14
30	896	918.28	-22.28
31	869	913.83	-44.83
32	825	904.86	-79.86
33	871	888.89	-17.89
34	1050	885.31	164.69
35	1019	918.25	100.75
36	891	938.40	-47.40
37	823	928.92	-105.92
38	839	907.74	-68.74
39	913	893.99	19.01
40	1107	897.79	209.21
41	748	939.63	-191.63
42	700	901.31	-201.31
43	883	861.04	21.96
44	1028	865.44	162.56
45	938	897.95	40.05
46	816	905.96	-89.96
47	1098	887.97	210.03
48	1010	929.97	80.03
49	931	945.98	-14.98
50	951	942.98	8.02

Figure 13 - Graph of actual and forecasted export demand using SES method

FORECASTING THE OEM DEMAND

OEM data, unlike Domestic and Export demand is by quarter. By plotting the data on a graph, we can also observe a trend for OEM.

Figure 14 - Line graph showing quarterly OEM demand for 4 years

Figure 15 - Line graph showing yearly OEM demand by quarter

Table 15 - OEM quarterly data grouped by year

	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
Y1	174	250	260	370
Y2	599	470	580	620
Y3	630	650	590	704
Y4	733	600	700	813

Table 16 shows the output when regression is run using OEM demand. Compared with Domestic and Export, the Standard Error is lower for OEM demand. The coefficient value per quarter is at 38. The residual plot on Figure 17 shows equal variance as we move along the horizontal line.

Table 16 - OEM demand regression output in Excel

SUMMARY OUTPUT							
<i>Regression Statistics</i>							
Multiple R	0.90864682						
R Square	0.825639044						
Adjusted R Square	0.814014981						
Standard Error	91.65621242						
Observations	17						
<i>ANOVA</i>							
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>		
Regression	1	596700.0221	596700.0221	71.02843	4.50693E-07		
Residual	15	126012.9191	8400.861275				
Total	16	722712.9412					
<i>Coefficients</i>							
	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>	<i>Lower 95.0%</i>	<i>Upper 95.0%</i>
Intercept	228.7573529	46.49716505	4.919812911	0.000185	129.6509916	327.8637143	129.6509916
Quarter	38.24264706	4.537658676	8.427836862	4.51E-07	28.57085654	47.91443758	28.57085654

Figure 16 - Actual OEM demand vs predicted OEM demand

Figure 17 - Quarterly residual plot for OEM demand

The next method used for OEM demand is Moving Averages for 3 and 5 values. It is a simple method for smoothing “past history” data (Makridakis et al., 1998). The output and graphs for this method are shown below.

Table 16 - Moving average values for OEM demand

Quarter	OEM Demand	MA3	MA5
1	174	0	0
2	250	0	0
3	260	0	0
4	370	228	0
5	599	293	0
6	470	410	331
7	580	480	390
8	620	550	456
9	630	557	528
10	650	610	580
11	590	633	590
12	704	623	614
13	733	648	639
14	600	676	661
15	700	679	655
16	813	678	665
17	997	704	710
18	837	837	769
19	882	882	789
20	905	905	846
21	875	875	887

Figure 17 - Graph of OEM demand vs forecast using moving average method

CONCLUSION

In order to measure the error of the methods used, RMSE (root mean square error) is computed. Table 17 shows a comparison of the results for Domestic Data. Based on the outcome, decomposition has shown the lowest RMSE value making it a best fit for Domestic Demand data.

Table 17 - Summary of forecasting results for domestic demand

	SUMMARY OF FORECASTS - DOMESTIC		
	Regression	Holt Winters	Decomposition
F51	2868	2301	2507
F52	2904	2356	2530
F53	2939	2507	2910
F54	2975	2309	3501
F55	3011	2931	3200
F56	3047	2630	2583
F57	3082	2617	3654
F58	3118	2309	2711
F59	3154	2407	3056
F60	3190	3408	3953
F61	3225	2767	3671
F62	3261	2635	3674
RMSE	309	328	192

Table 18 shows a comparison of the results for Export Data. Between regression and SES method, regression has shown lower RMSE and is a better fit for Export Data.

Table 18 - Summary of forecasting results for export demand

	SUMMARY OF FORECASTS - EXPORT	
	Regression	SES
F51	888	952
F52	886	952
F53	885	952
F54	883	952
F55	882	952
F56	880	952
F57	879	952
F58	877	952
F59	876	952
F60	874	952
F61	873	952
F62	871	952
RMSE	109	113

Table 19 compares the results of running regression and moving averages for OEM Demand. For this data set, regression also exhibits the lowest RMSE value and is the best fit for this type of data.

Table 19 - Summary of forecasting results for OEM demand

SUMMARY OF FORECASTS - OEM			
	Regression	MA3	MA5
F18	917	837	769
F19	905	882	789
F20	994	905	846
F21	1012	875	887
RMSE	86	138	136

Based on the results above, it can be deduced that the regression method provides more versatility, ease of use, and greater accuracy in forecasting. While other methods are simple to use and do not require the use of tools or programs, certain limitations arise depending on the type and nature of data to be analysed.

However, caution must be taken so as not to fall into the trap of “to a man with a hammer every problem looks like a nail” and not solely rely on regression methods for forecasting.

APPENDIX

For this paper, the data evaluated is a small set only. In the real world and businesses, it should be noted that large datasets are being processed. Big data are large data sets that are analysed computationally in order to gain significant insights and information (Mayer-Schönberger and Cukier, 2014). When handling data sets, time, complexity, effort, fit of algorithm, and space should be considered (Chambers et al., 1971; Mayer-Schönberger and Cukier, 2014).

The main tool used for this analysis is Excel and the methods used are limited to regression, exponential smoothing, and regression methods. Nowadays, most of data analysis is handled by computers. The portability of a forecasting method to be run on multiple platforms and programming languages should be considered. Some programs like R, Python, Julia, Scala and other tools provide built-in libraries that make running these computations faster (Costa, 2020; R Foundation, 2021). It should be considered by the analyst and user that certain tools and programs enable greater accuracy of results and can handle large amounts of datasets.

Lastly, while forecasting methods are crucial in a company's decision making it should not solely be the source of insights (Fildes & Goodwin, 2007). Businesses must keep in mind that there are limitations to predictions and human biases tend to cloud these judgments. Developing alternative plans and framework augmented with forecasting results are key in making resilient future-oriented decisions for businesses (Makridakis et al., 2009).

REFERENCES

- ANDERSON, D., SWEENEY, D., WILLIAMS, T., WISNIEWSKI, M., PIERRON, X., 2017. *An introduction to management science: Quantitative approaches to decision making*. 3 edn. Hampshire: Cengage Learning
- CHAMBERS, J., MULLICK, S., and SMITH, D., 1971. *How to Choose the Right Forecasting Technique*. Available at <https://hbr.org/1971/07/how-to-choose-the-right-forecasting-technique>. [Accessed 30 December 2021]
- COSTA, C., 2020. Top Programming Languages for Data Science in 2020. Available at: <https://towardsdatascience.com/top-programming-languages-for-data-science-in-2020-3425d756e2a7>. [Accessed 30 December 2021]
- FERRARA, L., 2014. Forecasting business cycles. *International journal of forecasting* (0169-2070), 30 , p. 517.
- FILDES, R., and GOODWIN, P., 2007a. "Against your better judgment? How organizations can improve their use of management judgment in forecasting". *Interfaces*, 37(6), pp .570–576. <https://doi.org/10.1287/inte.1070.0309>
- FILDES, R., and GOODWIN, P., 2007b, "Good and bad judgment in forecasting: lessons from four companies", *Foresight: The International Journal of Applied Forecasting*, vol. 8, pp. 5-10.
- GARDNER, E. S., and MCKENZIE, E., 1985. "Forecasting trends in time series". *Management Science*, 31(10), 1237–1246. <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.31.10.1237>
- GARDNER, E. S., 1985. "Exponential smoothing: The state of the art." *Journal of Forecasting*, 4(1), pp. 1–28. <https://doi.org/10.1002/for.3980040103>
- GARDNER, E. S., 2006. "Exponential smoothing: The state of the art — Part II." *International Journal of Forecasting*, 22, 637–666. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijforecast.2006.03.005>
- HOLT, C. E., 1957. *Forecasting seasonals and trends by exponentially weighted averages* (O.N.R. Memorandum No. 52). Carnegie Institute of Technology, Pittsburgh USA. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijforecast.2003.09.015>
- HYNDMAN, R.J., and ATHANASOPOULOS, G., 2021. *Forecasting: principles and practice*, 3rd edition, OTexts: Melbourne, Australia. OTexts.com/fpp3. [Accessed 12 December 2021].
- MAKRIDAKIS, S., HOGARTH, R.M. and GABA, A., 2009. "Forecasting and uncertainty in the economic and business world", *International journal of forecasting*, vol. 25, no. 4, pp. 794-812.

MAKRIDAKIS, S., HOGARTH,, R.M. and GABA, A., 2010. "Why forecasts fail. What to do instead", *MIT Sloan management review*, vol. 51, no. 2, pp. 83.

MAKRIDAKIS, S., WHEELRIGHT, S., and HYNDMAN, R., 1998. *Forecasting: Methods and Applications*. 3rd edn. New York: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.

MAYER-SCHÖNBERGER, V., and CUKIER, K., 2014. *Big Data: A Revolution That Will Transform How We Live, Work, and Think*. New York: Houghton Mifflin Harcourt.

R FOUNDATION., 2021. What is R? Available at: <https://www.r-project.org/about.html>. [Accessed 30 December 2021]

WINTERS, P. R., 1960. "Forecasting sales by exponentially weighted moving averages." *Management Science*, 6(3), pp. 324–342. <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.6.3.324>